

COS4BIO

Training & capacity building resources

Cos4Cloud Services

About the Cos4Bio system & user guide

This is a system and user guide to [Cos4Bio](#), a service that integrates biodiversity observations from multiple citizen observatories into one place. This provides easier access to large number of observations saving time while supporting the expert community in the species identification process.

Description

Cos4Bio is a service that integrates biodiversity observations from multiple citizen observatories (COs) into one place. This provides easier access for citizen science experts to view and identify a large number of biodiversity observations from different sources in a single place while interacting with CO communities and contributing their knowledge about each species.

Cos4Bio has been developed by [Bineo Consulting](#) as part of [Cos4Cloud](#), a European Horizon 2020 funded project. The Cos4Cloud project developed [thirteen services](#) boosting citizen science technological services to help increase and improve the quantity and quality of observations.

Cos4Bio is one of the three services developed by Bineo, **Cos4Bio** and **Cos4Env** are services that combine observations from citizen observatories focused on biodiversity (Cos4Bio) and environmental (Cos4Env) data which allows experts to spend less time accessing and searching data. The other is the Data Use Notification Service ([DUNS](#)) a service that registers the use of observations downloaded from the **Cos4Bio** and pass info back to the COs where the observations originated from.

Service Coordinator

Cos4Cloud Coordinator

The following content has been provided to help guide users of this service.

WHAT IS COS4BIO?

Cos4Bio is a co-designed, interoperable and open-source service that collects biodiversity information from multiple citizen observatories in one place. This allows experts to access many observations of biodiversity from a single site.

Observations in **Cos4Bio** are from citizen observatories integrated in the **Cos4Bio** service, including COs involved in Cos4Cloud i.e. [Pl@ntNet](#) and [Natusfera](#). It links to species lists defined by GBIF, the Global Biodiversity Information Facility which includes more than 3 and a half million accepted names of species worldwide, this unifies species lists from the different observatories.

WHO IS THIS SERVICE FOR AND WHAT ARE THE BENEFITS?

Cos4Bio is a service that enables COs to integrate biodiversity observations, it is aimed at expert users or users with knowledge of biodiversity, who want to collaborate in species identification by providing information on observations added by users on these different COs. Key benefits of this service include:

- Consolidates observations on one site: and this allows experts to search for, comment on and identify species, all from one place this makes it easier for access reducing the time spent
- Allows users to search for and download observations (this does not include pictures) from one portal which also recognises and notifies each observation's authorship.
- Enhances the power of citizen observatories providing access to better trained algorithms than databases with only the information of a single observatory.

HOW DOES IT WORK?

Citizen scientists, biological recorders, experts etc capture and share observations of biodiversity on using COs, where these are hosted. **Cos4Bio** integrates data from multiple COs in one portal, unifying information from different observatories in a standardised format i.e. under the same structure e.g., species name, location, etc.

When a CO is integrated into **Cos4Bio** observations that appear are linked directly using an API; this data is not stored but available for visualisation, validation, or downloading. Once logged in the portal, users can search the observations they are interested in, using multiple criteria i.e. species name, location etc. They can contribute comments and identifications in one place and once posted in **Cos4Bio** this is automatically added on the CO platform the observation is linked. For example, if a citizen science expert identifies a species through Cos4Bio and that is from Natusfera, it will automatically notify the user on Natusfera of the identification.

Final validation will always be done through the CO itself, using established criteria which varies based on the specification of the CO. For example, some algorithms require a certain degree of expertise to validate the species' name, but other algorithms ask for many identifications of the same observation to validate it, etc.

Cos4Bio also provides easier access to a wide range of data which users can download data in standardised format for research, reports etc. For example, if a scientist wants to carry out a study on the distribution of particular species in a particular area, they could use **Cos4Bio** to access and download the observations regardless of the citizen science observatory or country they come from. Data downloads includes the URL of the image and observations linked from the host CO, guided by their Terms and Conditions of use.

HOW TO USE COS4BIO - A STEP BY STEP GUIDE

Cos4Bio is a service that can be used by COs that would like to integrate their observations with other platforms, as well as by expert users or users with knowledge of biodiversity, who want to collaborate in species identification. This guide is for users of the **Cos4Bio** platform.

Citizen observatories interested in integrating their CO within **Cos4Bio** can see information related to the [Cos4Bio API](#). Contact: info@bineo-consulting.com

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GO TO THE COS4BIO WEBSITE AND LOG-IN:

Go to the [Cos4Bio website](#).

To get started select a language of choice and browse the latest observations:

Click on the log-in button and go through the sign in process:

Log-in access to **Cos4Bio** is via [AUTHENIX](#), a Cos4Cloud user authentication service.

For further information about **AUTHENIX** go to the website [here](#). Where the [Privacy Policy](#) and [Terms of use](#) are available.

Select the preferred login option.

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LOG-IN, SET UP A USER PROFILE AND EXPLORE ACTIVITY:

Once logged in go to the *user profile* button and complete the information requested and click *update* to save any changes. **Cos4Bio** give visibility to contributions made by each expert, and information about the contributor is made available on identifications and comments made, as well as details about their activity i.e. searches and downloads.

For additional Log-in support, see [this video](#):

Explore and view user activity from the [Dashboard](#):

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USE COS4BIO FEATURES:

Cos4Bio is a service that allows experts to access biodiversity observations from multiple citizen observatories in a single place. Features that support this include:

Search and filter observations: this allows users to specify search information by location i.e. place name, species name, the CO platform, type of species i.e. group.

Other options to filter or search: Other filter and search options can be applied, these include quality of the observation, quality / purpose of the search i.e. research, casual, with geolocation or photos.; the type of licence of the photos or the date / timeline. A combination of filters can also be used at the same time.

For further help with filtering and searching on **Cos4Bio** view [this video](#).

04 VIEW OBSERVATIONS:

In **Cos4Bio** summary details about each observation are visible from the snapshot view on the front page as well as on each observation when opened from a filtered search. Observation information summarised in this view includes: image, date posted in the citizen observatory, number of comments it has, number of images in each observation, name of the citizen observatory and coordinates. See video for further [help and support](#).

05 MAKE COMMENTS AND IDENTIFY SPECIES:

Open the observation, go to the *comment* or *identification* area, to add an identification at the bottom in the search bar indicate the name of the species and search for the species name, see example below:

To add a comment type in the Comments box. Remember to click “Send” when finished to save the changes made. The information is automatically added to the observation in the source CO it comes from, see example below:

For further help and support adding a comment or identification see [this video](#).

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SEARCH, VIEW AND DOWNLOAD OBSERVATIONS:

After applying selected filters and searching for observations, results can be downloaded as a csv file with links to the observations directing to the source CO:

Select the required filter options, as demonstrated in the example below:

Click *search* to show the results:

Click the *Download* button on the right and select the reason / purpose of use from the options available. After selecting the preferred option, click *Download* at the bottom to generate a csv file, as demonstrated below:

INFORMATION AND FURTHER SUPPORT

Introduction to this Cos4Cloud service: <https://cos4cloud-eosc.eu/services/cos4bio/>

Cos4Bio help, support and user guide: <https://cos4bio.eu/en/help.html>

About Cos4Bio: <https://cos4bio.eu/en/about.html>

Contact: info@bineo-consulting.com

Cos4Bio Terms and Conditions: <https://cos4bio.eu/en/terms.html>

Cos4Bio API: <https://cos4bio.eu/apidoc/index.html>

Cos4Bio Code repository: <https://github.com/Bineo-Consulting/Cos4Cloud>

Access this service from the EOSC Marketplace: Cos4Bio: <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/cos4bio>

Get the Cos4Cloud infographic for this service: [Cos4Bio Infographic](#)

Additional resources: [About the Cos4Cloud Toolbox and Evidence Hub](#)

This system and user guide is a training resource for Cos4Bio, one of the technological services co-designed by the Cos4Cloud project (<https://cos4cloud-eosc.eu/>). **Title: Cos4Bio System and User Guide.** Service Coordinator: Bineo Consulting. This guide is one of the Training and Capacity Building resources in the Cos4Cloud Toolbox & Evidence Hub developed by the Open University in collaboration with project partners. Contact: cos4cloud-toolbox@open.ac.uk.

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